

IMPLEMENTATION OF A SECURITY MECHANISM IN MICROSERVICES ARCHITECTURE*Abdullayev R.**Azerbaijan Technical University, Baku, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

Microservices architecture has become an essential part of modern engineering and provides the basis for building scalable and responsive systems. This decentralized architecture enables smooth communication between the various systems and devices, but also poses significant security challenges. This study examines centralized identity and access management (IAM) to address modern security threats. The study aims to help developers respond to the challenges of decentralized security by implementing technical solutions such as Keycloak and standard authentication protocols such as OAuth2.0 and JWT. The results show that the centralized security layer reduces system failures and interruptions, which leads to increased efficiency in providing the necessary services.

Keywords: Microservices, Keycloak, IAM, OAuth2.0, JWT, API security.

Introduction. Microservices architecture has become the cornerstone of modern engineering and enables organizations to build highly scalable, flexible and resilient systems. Unlike traditional monolithic applications, microservices break down large software applications into smaller, self-contained services that communicate with each other over APIs. This decentralized structure offers a number of advantages, including greater scalability, faster development cycles and easier maintenance. However, the very nature of microservices - distributed, networked and loosely linked - also poses major security challenges. Each microservice often uses sensitive data such as user credentials, financial information or personal identifiers, and the proliferation of API endpoints increases the scope for cybercriminals to attack. Common threats against microservices include malware, phishing, token theft, abuse of APIs, and attempts to gain access through an unauthenticated network connection [1].

The security of microservices is substantially more complex than that of monolithic applications due to several factors:

1. **Distributed Data and Services:** Sensitive information is distributed across multiple services and databases, making it difficult to enforce consistent access control.
2. **Multiple Communication Channels:** Microservices rely heavily on APIs and network communications, which, if not properly secured, may be exploitable by attackers.
3. **Heterogeneous Technology Stack:** Different services can use different programming languages, frameworks and databases, which makes it difficult to implement a single security policy.
4. **Dynamic Scaling and Deployment:** Services are often deployed, updated, and scaled up dynamically, which poses challenges for traditional verification and monitoring mechanisms.

Identity and Access Management (IAM) is a key strategy for addressing these problems. By centralizing authentication and authorization, IAM ensures that sensitive resources can only be accessed by authorized users and services, while providing audit, logging and compliance mechanisms. Among the available IAM solutions, Keycloak has become the widely adopted open source platform for securing modern applications. It supports industry standard protocols such as OAuth2.0, OpenID Connect, and JWT, and allows developers to implement single sign-on (SSO), token authentication, and granular access control for distributed services [2].

The aim of this research is to provide a comprehensive understanding of centralized IAM and to explore practical solutions to ensure the provision of microservices in the real world. By embedding Keycloak in the microservice architecture, this study aims to demonstrate how the centralized layer of security can reduce the risk of unauthorized access, simplify identity management and increase operational efficiency. In addition, the research assesses how automation of authentication and token validation can reduce system failures, minimize human error and increase the overall reliability of distributed systems. The aim of this work is ultimately to provide developers, system architects and organizations with actionable guidance to build secure, resilient and manageable microservices applications.

Experimental part

The research involves establishing a centralized authentication strategy using the Keycloak platform. The experimental setup follows a specific logic where the API Gateway acts as the central intelligence of the security layer.

The working principle of the proposed system is as follows:

Figure 1: Implementation of Keycloak-based Security Flow in Microservices

- **Authentication:** The Client initiates a Login request directly to the Keycloak server. This may be done y the web interface or by program [3].

Figure 2. Keycloak Sign-in Interface

We send credentials such as username, password, and client_secret via Postman to the token endpoint to receive an authorization token.

Figure 3. Keycloak Sign-in Interface

number of concurrent users increases, the central authentication mechanism maintains a consistent response time thanks to stateless JWT authentication and optimized caching strategies [5]. Compared to a decentralized authentication model, where each service independently validates credentials, a centralized model reduces the number of cryptographic operations and reduces network overhead between services.

The coverage of security cases has been significantly extended beyond basic authentication. The system in place implements advanced password policies that are in line with modern security standards.

Figure 6. Password Policy Configuration Interface in Keycloak Admin Console

These controls significantly reduce the risks associated with credential re-use, brute force attacks, and unauthorized access attempts. In simulated abuse scenarios, such as repeated logon failures or attempts to re-use passwords, the system consistently blocked non-compliant actions, demonstrating strong enforcement of the security rules.

Moreover, centralization improves the behavior of the system during partial failures. If the individual microservice is not available, authentication and authorization services will remain unaffected, as they are isolated and deployed independently. This architectural separation increases fault tolerance and ensures that safety mechanisms remain operational even after the service has ceased to function. Observation has confirmed that the token expiration and replacement mechanisms continue to function properly under stress and failure simulations, which prevents session hijacking and unlimited token abuse.

Another important result is improved auditability. As all identity-related transactions go through a central IAM provider, the system maintains consolidated log-in attempts, token issuance, password changes, and access decisions. This single audit trail enhances compliance readiness and facilitates incident response procedures.

Overall, the results show that the Keycloak-integrated architecture not only improves endpoint protection, but also creates a scalable, maintainable and policy-driven security ecosystem that is suitable for enterprise and e-government systems.

- Password history enforcement prevents users from reusing their previous passwords. For example, if the policy stores the last 10 passwords, the user cannot reuse any of those 10 previously defined credentials.
- Complexity requirements ensure passwords contain a combination of uppercase and lowercase letters, numeric digits, and special characters [4].
- Minimum length constraints and expiration policies further strengthen protection [4].
- Account lockout mechanisms limit brute-force attempts after repeated failed login trials.

Recommendations and Future Work

The following strategic and technical recommendations are proposed to further strengthen and develop the security position of microservice systems:

1. Full centralization of security management

Re-architect the environment to rely exclusively on a single centralised IAM program for authentication, authorization, and policy enforcement for all microservices. This approach avoids duplicate security configurations across services and ensures consistent application of the policy. Future improvements may include dynamic updates of policies without requiring a service move.

2. Standardization of single sign-on (SSO) Adopt single sign-on as a compulsory standard for business and e-government platforms. SSO improves the user experience by allowing seamless access to multiple services using a single authentication session, while at the same time maintaining high security through authentication by means of tokens. The integration of SSO with role-based and attribute-based access control mechanisms can provide granular authorization without compromising usability.

3. Automated Security Validation and Policy Enforcement

Automatically validate security configurations through CI and CD channels. Automated checks may verify the password policy, token lifetime, role mapping, and endpoint protection rules prior to deployment. This reduces human configuration errors,

minimizes system failures, and improves reliability of service provision.

4. Enhanced Monitoring and Observability

Integrate advanced monitoring tools for continuous monitoring of authentication latency, token validation times, login failure patterns and suspicious activity trends. The combination of centralized logging and real-time alert systems will enhance proactive threat detection and incident response capabilities.

5. Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) Expansion

Extend the system with mandatory multi-factor authentication to sensitive services. Future work may include biometric authentication or hardware-based encryption for high risk operations.

6. Adaptive and Risk-Based Authentication

Future research may explore AI-driven adaptive authentication mechanisms. By analyzing behavioral patterns (e.g., unusual login location or device change), the system could dynamically increase authentication requirements when risk levels rise.

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